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Research Article

**PHARMACOGNOSTICAL, PHYTOCHEMICAL AND WOUND
HEALING STUDY ON ETHANOLIC EXTRACT OF LEAF OF
XANTHIUM STRUMARIUM. Linn****Dr.J. Jaslin Edward., M.Pharm., Ph.D., Janani.K.S, Shamlin E. Ashwini, Abi.A, Mathan
Kumar.M, Astilin lijo.L, Logesh.L**Sun College Of Pharmacy And Research Centre, Vellamodi, Kanyakumari, Tamil Nadu,
India.**Abstract:**

Background: Wound healing is a multifaceted process involving various stages, including inflammation, tissue regeneration and remodelling. This quest for the effective wound healing agents has led to the exploration of traditional medicine and herbal remedies. *Xanthium strumarium*, a plant species known for its medicinal properties, has gained attention for its potential benefits in wound healing. This study aims to investigate the wound healing potential of *Xanthium strumarium* leaf extract.

Materials And Methods: *Xanthium strumarium* leaves were collected from putheri, kanyakumari district and authenticated by experts. These leaves were then processed into a powder and Soxhlet extraction was performed using various solvents including Petroleum ether, Chloroform, Ethyl acetate and 70% Ethanol. The extracts were subsequently formulated into 0.5% and 1% ointments. The wound healing activity of these ointments was assessed in adult male albino rats, with 1% silver sulfadiazine serving as a standard comparison.

Result: The study yielded significant results, demonstrating the wound healing potential of *Xanthium strumarium* leaf extracts. The 0.5% ointment showed complete wound healing on 15th day, while the 1% ointment achieved the same on the 14th day. In comparison, the standard drug, 1% silver sulfadiazine, healed wounds on the 12th day. Physicochemical analysis and qualitative chemical tests revealed promising results, indicating the presence of bioactive compounds that may contribute to the wound healing properties of *Xanthium strumarium*.

Conclusion: The findings of this study suggest that *Xanthium strumarium* leaf extracts possess potential wound healing properties, justifying further research for therapeutic applications. The results demonstrate the efficacy of *Xanthium strumarium* as a natural remedy for wound healing, highlighting its potential as a valuable resource in traditional medicines.

Keywords: Wounds, Soxhlet apparatus, Animals, Extracts.

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INTRODUCTION:

In recent years there has been a significant shift in the global trend towards natural medicine. According to the world health organization (WHO), 80% of the world's population relies on traditional medicine for their primary health care needs. Wound care remains a significant challenge in modern medicine, with imperfect healing posing serious consequences. According to the WHO, approximately 5 million people died from wound related complications each year, highlighting the need for effective innovative wound management strategies.

Plants are rich in bioactive phytochemicals, which can be classified into several distinct groups. These groups include Alkaloids, Carotenoids, Phenolic compounds, Steroids, Flavanoids, Saponins, Tannins and Terpenoids. Each of these phytochemical families plays a unique role in the healing process.

The Therapeutic effects of these compounds are multifaceted, targeting various stages of wound healing. They exhibit potent Anti-inflammatory, Antimicrobial and Antioxidant properties, which in turn facilitate collagen synthesis, promote cell growth and support the formation of new blood vessels.^[1]

A Wound is a disruption in the skin's integrity, often resulting from physical, thermal or medical factors. This disruption can compromise the skin's natural barrier function, making it susceptible to infection and further complications.

There are two primary categories of wounds; they are acute wounds and chronic wounds. Acute wounds are typically characterized by their ability to heal within a predictable timeframe, usually 8-12 weeks. These wounds often result from injuries, burns or chemical damage and the healing process tends to follow a standard progression. In Contrast, chronic wounds exhibit delayed healing, often persisting beyond the expected timeframe. These Wounds can lead to significant scarring and are frequently associated with underlying medical conditions, such as diabetes. The complex nature of chronic wounds requires a comprehensive approach to management and treatment.^[2]

The wound healing phases is a complex, dynamic series of events that involves multiple phases. Phase 1 is a Haemostasis (0-4 days is more like inflammation starts but haemostasis is immediate).The second phase is inflammation (0-4 days), Third phase is proliferation (4-21 days) and the fourth phase is remodeling (21 days -2 years).

Xanthium strumarium, an Asteraceae family member, has been chosen for this study due to its widespread use in traditional medicine for various ailments. This plant, native to India, is known by multiple local names and is utilized to treat diverse health issues, including skin conditions, infections and rheumatic disorders. Phytochemical analysis reveals a rich array of bioactive compounds such as xanthatin and β -sitosterol, contributing to its medicinal properties. Over 170 compounds have been identified, showcasing its complex composition and potential therapeutic applications. Xanthium^[5, 8] strumarium leaves and roots exhibit various therapeutic properties, while its seeds are used to address bladder issues. The plant also finds used in domestic application, such as tea preparation and insect repellents. The bioactive compounds present in X.strumarium have analgesic, anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial effects, thus making X.strumarium as a valuable resource for treating wounds and other health issues.^[4] This study investigates the Pharmacognostical, Phytochemical and wound healing study on ethanolic extract of leaf of Xanthium strumarium.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

1) COLLECTION OF PLANT MATERIAL

Fresh leaves of Xanthium strumarium were found in roadsides, wastelands, and along waterways^[6] (Fig No: 1). They were collected from the plain area of putheri in kanyakumari district, Tamil Nadu, India. During the month of February 2025. The leaves were collected during the flowering and fruiting stage, ensuring optimal phytochemical content. They were carefully harvested without causing harm to the plant or its surroundings, following sustainable collection practices. The collected leaves were cleaned with distilled water to remove any dirt or debris, and then shade-dried for 20 days to preserve their chemical constituents. The dried leaves were then grinded to a fine powder^[9] (Fig No: 2).

FIG No.1: Xanthium strumarium Linn

2) AUTHENTICATION

The botanical identity of the collected *Xanthium strumarium* leaves was authenticated as *Xanthium strumarium* by referring to the standard botanical literature, Flora of the Presidency of Madras (J.S. Gamble, Vol. I-III) and other relevant taxonomic references. This authentication process was carried out under the expert guidance of Dr. R. Sunitha Sajini, Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, Women's Christian College, Nagercoil. Morphological and microscopic characteristics, such as leaf shape, size, and venation, were carefully examined to confirm the identity of the plant material. A voucher specimen (SCPRC/COG/HER/001/2025) was deposited in the

herbarium at sun college of pharmacy and research centre, kanyakumari district for future reference and verification. The voucher specimen includes details such as collection date, location, and habitat, ensuring accurate documentation and traceability.

3) PREPARATION OF PLANT EXTRACTS

The collected leaves were rinsed thoroughly several times with tap water and finally with distilled water to ensure cleanliness. After washing, the plant materials were air-dried in the shade for approximately seven days. Once fully dried, the leaves were ground into a fine powder suitable for soxhlet extraction as shown in Figure No 2.

FIG No.2 : Fine powder of the leaves of *Xanthium strumarium*

A total of 500 g of powdered *Xanthium strumarium* was weighed accurately and stored in an airtight container to prevent moisture absorption before extraction.^[6] This fine powder (500 g) was used for the extraction process, which was carried out using a Soxhlet apparatus (Fig No: 3) with increasing polarity of solvents like Petroleum ether, Chloroform, Ethyl acetate and 70% Ethanol. The extraction parameters, such as temperature, time, and solvent ratio, were optimized to ensure maximum yield of bioactive compounds.^[7]

FIG No.3: Extraction done by soxhlet apparatus

4) PREPARATION OF HERBAL OINTMENT AND STANDARD USED

Simple ointment containing 50 mg/g (0.5%), 100 mg/g (1%) of EEXS (fig no:4) prepared by trituration method in a ceramic mortar and pestle using white soft paraffin base, obtained from S.D. Fine chemicals, India (Cooper and Gunn's, 1987). For this 500/1000mg of EEXS was incorporated with 10g of the base. Silver sulfadiazine 100mg/g ointment obtained from Rexin pharmaceuticals Pvt. Ltd. was used as standard drug for comparing the wound healing potential of extract in different animal models. ^[10]

FIG No.4: Preparation of simple ointment, 0.5 % and 1% ointment by using ethanol Extract of Xanthium strumarium

5) PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDIES

Animals

Adult male albino rats weighing about 200-250g were used in this study. They were maintained in clean, sterile, polycarbonate cages and fed with commercial pellet rat chow (M/S Hindustan lever limited, Bangalore, India) and water ad libitum. The study was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC) of Cape bio lab and Research Centre, Marthandam bearing the approval number CBLRC/IAEC/06/01 - 2025 which follows the guidelines of Committee for Control and Supervision of Experimental Animals (CCSEA).^[10]

Grouping of animals

Four groups of animals containing six animals in each group were used for the excision wound models. The animals of group G₁ considered as control, group G₂, G₃ were considered as test group, G₄ considered as standard group and were treated respectively.^[10]

Wound healing property of extracts by excision wound model

Circular wounds of approximately 10mm diameter were inflicted on the cleared skin cutting under mild ether anesthesia (Ketamine 75mg/g, Xylazine 5mg/kg). The areas of the wounds were traced (sq.mm) immediately by placing a transparent paper over the wound. The tracing was then shifted to graph paper, from which the wound area was evaluated. This will be taken as the initial wound area reading.

G₁ Simple ointment I.P applied topically.

G₂ EEES 50mg/g (0.5%) ointment applied topically.

G₃ EEES 100mg/g (1%) ointment applied topically

G₄ Treated with silver sulfadiazine Ointment 1% applied topically

All the samples were applied twice in a day for 15 days and wound contraction were measured. The wound area of each animal was measured on 2nd, 4th, 6th, 8th, 10th, 12th, 14th and 15th post wounding measurements of wound area. Day 15 was considered as the end point of the acute healing process.^[12] The percentage of wound contraction was calculated by this following formula.

$$\% \text{ of wound contraction} = \frac{\text{Initial wound size} - \text{Specific day wound size}}{\text{Initial wound size}} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

Results obtained from wound model have been expressed as mean \pm SEM and the treated group was compared with control group. The results were analyzed statistically using one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's Multiple Comparison Test, to

analyze the differences between the treated and control. The data were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.^[11]

WOUND HEALING EFFECT

Wound healing is a systematic process of events which repair the damaged tissue partially or completely. Wound healing occurs in three stages: inflammation, proliferation, and remodelling. The healing process begins with the blood clotting and is completed with remodelling of the cellular layers of the skin. However, the wound healing process may be suppressed by the presence of ROS or infection by microorganism. The type of cells which injured or damaged will be first recruited at the site of injury (Gupta, 2002). The cell injury is due to antimicrobial defense are cellular damage by peroxidation of membrane lipids (Russo 2002 and Choi 2009). Appropriate methods of wound healing are essential for the restoration of damaged tissue anatomical continuity and disturbed functional status of the skin (Meenakshi 2006). Wound healing agents research is one of the developing areas in modern biomedical sciences and many traditional practitioners across world particularly in countries like India and China have more valuable information of many plants for treating wounds and burns (Kumar, 2007).

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the wound healing potential of ethanolic extract of *Xanthium strumarium* (EEES) on circular excision wound model using rat.

6) PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CONSTANTS

The procedures recommended in IP, 1996 and WHO guidelines, 1992 were followed to calculate the physicochemical constants like Ash values, Extractive values and loss on drying.^[9]

7) QUALITATIVE CHEMICAL TESTS

The Ethanol extracts obtained from the leaves of *Xanthium strumarium* was subjected to various chemical assays to identify the presence of Alkaloids, Carbohydrates, Proteins and amino acids, Glycosides, Flavanoids, Saponins, Tannins, Phenols, Terpenoids and steroids.^[8]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Wound healing is a natural response of injured skin, consists of complex interactive phases of inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling. The first response of the healing period is inflammation as a defense mechanism of the tissue, which provides a resistance to the microbial contaminations (Kondo, 2007). Excision wound models were employed for the

assessment of wound healing activity. In India sixty four ethnomedicinal plants are used for wound healing (Kumar, 2007). This model was used to evaluate the effect of the test samples on wound closure and contraction and consequently time of epithelialization. The effect was measured every 2 days of 15 post wounding days. The standard drug silver sulfadiazine 1% showed 100% healing on 12th day of wound incision whereas, test extract EEXS 0.5 %, 1% showed healing effect on 15th and 14th day respectively.

The results observed in present study were illustrated in Table 5. The results obtained from the present study revealed that, the ointment preparation of EEXS showed a better wound healing effect in rats when compared with control group. G₁ Simple ointment I.P used as a base for the preparation has shown 54.67±0.39 % wound healing activity on 15th day of treatment. The result revealed the fact that animals treated with EEXS exhibited a significant (*p<0.05) increased the percentage of wound healing power with respect to dose dependent manner when compared to control. Therefore, this wound healing

effect of EEXS may be due to its antioxidant properties. Flavonoids are well known active antioxidant compounds responsible for the inhibition of lipid peroxidation, which leads to prevention of the cell damage and increase in the viability of collagen fibrils (Getie, 2002 and Shetty, 2008). This is particularly important since the treated wounds should contract much faster (Swamy, 2007).

Table No 1 illustrates the physicochemical parameters, comprising ash values includes total ash, water soluble ash, acid insoluble ash and sulphated ash. Table 2 shows the Extractive values include water soluble extractive, ethanol soluble extractive and Ether soluble extractive and table 3 shows the result of drying parameters.

Xanthium strumarium leaves extracts were subjected to qualitative chemical tests for the detection of various phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, protein, amino acids, glycosides, flavanoids, saponins, tannin, phenol, terpenoids, steroids. The phytochemical screening results are shown in Table No 4.

Table No.1 : Ash values of Xanthium strumarium Leaves

S.NO	PARAMETER	PRACTICAL YIELD	PERCENTAGE YIELD
1	Total ash	0.61g	30.04%
		0.48g	24%
		0.57g	28.35%
2	Water soluble	0.33g	16.25%
3	Acid insoluble ash	0.2g	10%
4	Sulphated ash	0.3g	19.40%

Table No. 2: Extraction Values of Xanthium strumarium Leaves

S.NO	EXTRACTION VALUES	PRACTICAL YIELD	PERCENTAGE YIELD
1	Ethanol soluble extraction	0.10g	4.9%
2	Water soluble extraction	0.12g	5.9%
3	Ether soluble extraction	0.03g	1.47%

Table No. 3: Drying parameters of Xanthium strumarium Leaves

INITIAL WEIGHT	FINAL WEIGHT	LOSS ON DRYING	% OF LOSS ON DRYING
1g	0.86g	0.14g	1.4%

Table No. 4: Qualitative chemical analysis of phytoconstituents of the ethanolic extract of *Xanthium strumarium*

Treatment		Percentage of wound contraction							
Post wounding days	Dose mg/g	2	4	6	8	10	12	14	15
Control	Simple ointment	2.13±0.03*	10.21±0.49*	21.45±0.61*	30.52±0.80*	35.23±1.18*	43.54±0.55*	51.91±1.20*	54.67±0.39*
EEXS	0.5%	3.30±0.11	14.19±0.80*	32.92±0.68*	64.21±0.90*	77.40±0.09*	89.15±0.60*	95.32±0.50*	100*
EEXS	1%	6.16±0.67*	19.48±0.43*	38.25±1.24*	68.98±0.55*	79.84±0.96*	93.69±0.42*	100*	
Silver sulfadiazine	1%	9.40±0.71*	24.37±0.66*	46.93±0.58*	76.68±0.20*	85.27±0.42*	100*		

+ = positive - = negative

Table No.5: Effect of Ethanolic Extract of *Xanthium strumarium* (EEXS) on wound contraction

S NO	Tested Components	Results
1	Alkaloids	-
2	Carbohydrates	+
3	Protein and Amino acid	-
4	Glycosides	+
5	Tannins	+
6	Phenols	+
7	Flavonoids	+
8	Saponins	+
9	Terpenoids	+
10	Steroids	+

Wounds treated with 05% and 1% have shown increased rate of wound contraction

Values reported as mean ±SEM (n=6). The data were analyzed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test.

*p<0.05 as compared with control group.

CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully evaluated the pharmacognostical, phytochemical, and wound healing properties of the ethanolic extract of *Xanthium strumarium* L. leaves. Phytochemical screening confirmed the presence of flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, phenolic acids, and glycosides, all of which are known for their antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and wound healing properties.

The wound healing efficacy of the ethanolic extract was tested using an excision wound model in albino rats. The results demonstrated that the 1% ethanolic extract ointment exhibited significant wound

contraction, enhanced collagen synthesis, and faster epithelialization, comparable to the standard drug.

These findings validate the traditional medicinal use of *Xanthium strumarium* in wound care and highlight its potential as a natural alternative for wound healing formulations. However, further research, including clinical trials and mechanistic studies, is necessary to confirm its safety, efficacy, and standardization for therapeutic use.

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